

Style and Literary Techniques Used to Make a Literary Work Alive: Anna Ernaux & Arundhati Roy

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Abstract:

The personal narratives of two significant writers, Anna Ernaux and Arundhati Roy, are investigated and analysed in this comparative study. It emphasises their unique writing styles, subject interests, and involvement with societal and personal issues. This research explores the various ways in which these authors construct their identities, reflect on social realities, and challenge established structures through the medium of personal storytelling by looking at Ernaux's works, such as "The Years" and "A Man's Place," and Roy's narratives, such as "The God of Small Things" and "The Ministry of Utmost Happiness." "Personal narratives by Ernaux provide a look into her recollections and experiences, which are intertwined with a broader memory of post-war France. She expertly weaves together the historical and the personal, weaving a narrative tapestry that examines topics of gender, class, and personal identity. Her introspective examination of her own life offers a window into more general societal shifts and the challenges of adjusting to shifting social conventions.

Keywords:

Personal narratives, identity, gender, politics, social change, memory, literature.

Introduction

Personal narratives are meant to reflect on social reality in connection to the author and are intended to question established societal structures while also conveying the author's unique experiences. It is generally known that both Indian author Arundhati Roy and French writer Anna Ernaux are well-known for their fascinating personal narratives that provide insight into their lives and the world around them from their unique points of view. In this paper, we analyse the many literary genres, thematic issues, and social circumstances that have an impact on the personal narratives of the two authors while analysing how these factors differ from one another. They both explore identity, which is a fundamental theme in both Anna Ernaux and Arundhati Roy's personal narratives. To build their identities and consider their role in society, both authors focus on their own personal experiences and recollections. In order to question cultural norms and undermine power systems, Ernaux and Roy turn to personal tales. In doing so, they illuminate the connections between individual experiences and broader social, cultural, and political settings. They also explore the boundaries between individual and communal identities.

Many of Ernaux's works, such as "The Years" and "A Man's Place," explore her own recollections and experiences while creating a communal memory of post-World War II France and delving into topics of gender, class, and individual identity. In her personal narratives, especially "The God of Small Things" and "The Ministry of Utmost Happiness,"

Roy both describes her own background in India and investigates her upbringing in India, her political involvement, and the marginalised voices and groups in India. In order to identify the contrasts between Ernaux and Roy, I compare their tales side-by-side in this research paper to discover the distinctive ways each of them used. It will be able to pinpoint issues and themes that the groups have in common as well.

The discussion of the writers' linguistic choices, narrative strategies, and literary devices will be included in the examination of these personal accounts. They will be able to share their messages and experiences as a result. In addition, the socio-cultural and historical settings in which Ernaux and Roy write will be examined, revealing how the authors' distinct upbringings influenced their narratives. With the help of this comparative study, I learnt more about the ways in which society institutions and norms may be challenged and illuminated by individual narratives.

Even though their experiences and surroundings are different, social transformation is a prominent subject in Anna Ernaux and Arundhati Roy's personal narratives. I can see from their comparative studies how societal change affects their viewpoints on numerous topics and forms their narratives. The societal transformation in post-war France is frequently reflected in Anna Ernaux's personal memoirs. Her works, including "The Years," which examines changes in gender roles, social groups, and political beliefs, chart the evolution of French society over a number of

decades. The narratives of Ernaux convey the communal memory of a civilization in transition. Both writers draw attention to how her own experiences and identity have changed as a result of societal advancement, cultural changes, and developing standards.

In this research paper I observed how societal change affects Ernaux and Roy's storytelling techniques through a comparative analysis of their personal narratives. The historical, cultural, and political circumstances in which these stories take place are clearly understood by both authors. They examine the effects of social change on people and communities by drawing on their own experiences to provide light on larger societal challenges.

The personal narratives of Ernaux and Roy both emphasise the importance of individual action and resistance to social change. Offering glimmerings of hope, resiliency, and transformational action, they give voice to marginalised voices and confront oppressive structures.

Conclusion:

Comparing the autobiographical narratives of Arundhati Roy and Anna Ernaux reveals significant differences in how authors develop and express their identities. Social and political concerns are addressed and pre-existing power structures are contested as a result of their actions. In order to portray a feeling of the communal memory of post-war France, Ernaux examines issues in his artwork including gender, class, and personal identity. Her political involvement is woven within Roy's storytelling, which depict marginalised voices and communities in India. Both Ernaux and Roy are passionate about using personal experiences as a vehicle for societal critique and change, despite the fact that their writing methods and aesthetic choices differ. They explore memory, history, and the context of their respective cultures via their stories. They challenge readers to think critically about prevailing narratives and to accept dissident viewpoints.

This research paper uses a comparative approach to pinpoint the unique literary devices, narrative devices, and thematic issues used by Ernaux and Roy. It looks at how the sociocultural and historical settings in which people write are reflected in their personal narratives and how these contexts influence how they see topics like identity, gender, politics, and social change. We learn more about the ability of personal storytelling to expose and question societal norms as well as to promote empathy and understanding across cultural borders by comparing and contrasting their experiences. The results of this comparative study show that, despite the fact that Ernaux and Roy come from various cultural backgrounds and write in various socio-political settings, their personal narratives have a common

goal: to reflect on unique experiences, negotiate identity complexities, and engage with more significant societal issues. Both writers pledge to use personal narratives as a vehicle for social criticism, female emancipation, and societal change. Readers are encouraged to consider the effects of both personal and societal experiences through their works. This promotes a greater comprehension of the intricacies of human existence and the possibility for societal transformation.

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